

A review on simultaneous method development approach for Empagliflozin and Sitagliptin phosphate

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Abstract— Pharmaceutical analysis plays a crucial role during the whole process of drug development, from formulating new medications to stability testing and quality control. It helps us understand the content of different dosage forms, both quantitatively and qualitatively. By conducting a thorough review of existing literature, we lay the groundwork for a focused study on current research activities in this field. Diabetes is treated with antidiabetic drugs, that lessen blood glucose levels. Antidiabetic drugs are categorized as oral hypoglycemic drugs and insulin preparations. Therapeutic strategies that improve urine glucose excretion and reduce renal glucose reabsorption, such as sitagliptin phosphate and empagliflozin, may be used to decrease glucose-dependent insulin secretion and glucagon release. This review brings together information from previously published methods for analyzing sitagliptin phosphate and empagliflozin, whether on their own or alongside other medications. It highlights the various techniques that have been used in the past to better understand these drugs. It provides insights into the development of various analytical methods, including UV, HPLC, and HPTLC techniques. This information allows us to choose the best method for further research. This concise review is designed to help analysts pick the most effective approach for developing and validating their analytical methods.

Keywords— Sitagliptin phosphate, Empagliflozin, Analytical methods, UV, HPLC.

I. INTRODUCTION

Diabetes is a chronic metabolic illness that can harm the kidneys, eyes, nerves, heart, and blood vessels. Increased blood glucose levels mark it. Type 2 diabetes, characterised by inadequate or resistant insulin production, is most common in adults. Regardless of income level, type 2 diabetes (T2D) has increased in prevalence over the past 30 years in all countries. Type 1 diabetes (T1D) is a chronic condition brought on by insufficient or else no insulin production by the pancreas. This kind of diabetes is also called insulin-dependent DM or juvenile-onset diabetes. Diabetes patients require low-cost medical care, including insulin, in order to survive¹. During pregnancy, type 3 diabetes, sometimes referred to as gestational diabetes, develops, raises the risk of obesity in both the mother and her offspring, and can cause difficulties both during and after childbirth. The inability of the pancreas to produce insulin, which is essential in regulating blood sugar, leads to T1D. In contrast, when the body's cells don't react efficiently to insulin T2D develops, making it harder to manage blood sugar levels. Impaired fasting glycemia (IGT), which is in the range between normal and diabetes blood glucose levels, and impaired fasting glucose (IGG) are the two forms of glucose intolerance. That being said, the shift need not occur inevitably. Compared to people with normal blood sugar levels, those with IFG (Impaired Fasting Glucose) as well as IGT (Impaired Glucose Tolerance) are more probable to develop cardiovascular disease^[2-3]. A number of antidiabetic medications are shown in Figure 1 employed to treat diabetes.

Fig. 1 Classification of Antidiabetic Drug

SGLT-2 Inhibitors

SGLT-2 inhibitors can be taken orally to treat diabetes. T2D is regularly prescribed drug. If you have type 2 diabetes, oral prescription medications to control blood sugar authorized by U.S. Food and Drug Administration recognized as SGLT-2 (sodium-glucose cotransporter-2) inhibitors may be useful in conjunction with diet and exercise. SGLT-2 inhibitors, commonly referred to as gliflozins, help lower blood sugar levels by stopping your kidneys from reabsorbing the sugar your body makes^[4]. This means that more sugar is excreted in your urine, which can help manage blood sugar levels more effectively. The excess sugar is thus excreted through urine. SGLT-2 inhibitors are a novel category of medications which not only help lower blood sugar but also reduce blood cholesterol through prohibiting reabsorption of sugar in kidneys. By encouraging glucose excretion in urine, these medications effectively help manage blood sugar levels. Reduced blood pressure and diuresis are the outcomes of the osmotic action of glucose depletion. While they may also interact with SGLT-1 receptors in the gastrointestinal tract and proximal renal tubules, these medications selectively act on SGLT-2 receptors, which are present in the kidneys. These drugs, which are now widely available and licensed, have been demonstrated to considerably improve the kidney and cardiovascular systems in numerous subgroups of type 2 diabetic patients^[4-5]. Examples of SGLT-2 inhibitors are bexagliflozin, dapagliflozin, empagliflozin, canagliflozin, & ertugliflozin^[2].

Empagliflozin

Empagliflozin inhibits the SGLT-2 enzyme, which is necessary for kidneys for glucose reabsorption^[6]. In clinical practice, this medication is usually prescribed alongside other drugs, along with diet & exercise, to effectively manage T2DM (type 2 diabetes mellitus)⁷. The C- glycosyl compound empagliflozin contains a phenyl group (4-chloro-3-{4-[(3S)-tetrahydrofuran-3-yloxy]benzyl) and beta-glucosyl residue in its anomeric centre. (Figure 2 illustrates the structure of Empagliflozin). PubChem was created by Boehringer-Ingelheim. Four varieties are offered for sale: Synjardy (empagliflozin and metformin), Glyxambi (empagliflozin plus linagliptin), and Jardiance (empagliflozin). The drug was approved by the FDA in 2014^[2-8].

Fig. 2 Structure of Empagliflozin

DPP IV Inhibitor

GIP (Insulin-releasing polypeptide) is an example of an incretin hormone that enteroendocrine cells make and that triggers the release of insulin. Another is GLP-1 (glucagon-like peptide-1). DPP-4, an enzyme that quickly deactivates incretins, is the reason for the extremely short half-life ($t_{1/2}$). DPP-4 inhibitors work by preventing DPP-4 from acting enzymatically, which raises the amounts of GIP and GLP-1 that are active. As a result, they treat hyperglycemia in diabetic patients in a glucose-dependent way by increasing blood insulin and lowering serum glucagon. As a result, incretin-related therapies such as DPP-4 inhibitors are potential medications that help reduce glucose fluctuation in diabetes patients and have emerged as a new class of antidiabetic. Several studies have looked into how these inhibitors affect glycaemic management, whether used alone or with other drugs. Additionally, studies have shown that DPP-4 inhibitors can help improve blood sugar control while also reducing the chances of weight gain and low blood sugar episodes^[1]. Saxagliptin, Linagliptin, Alogliptin, Sitagliptin, and Vildagliptin are DPP-4 inhibitors (Gliptins)^[9].

Sitagliptin phosphate

Chemical properties of sitagliptin phosphate 6-dihydro[1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a]pyrazin-7(8H)-yl]-3-(2,4,5-trifluorophenyl)propan-1-one, (2S)-2-amino-1-[3 (trifluoromethyl)-5 (Figure 3 illustrates structure of Sitagliptin). One phosphate hydrate of butan-1^[10]. This hypoglycemic drug is classified as a DPP-4 inhibitor. For T2D treatment the DPP-4 inhibitors are a novel category of medication. By preventing breakdown of GIP as well as GLP-1, they improve glycaemic management by blocking incretin inactivation. Furthermore, they increase glucose-dependent insulin release while decreasing glucagon levels. The United States has approved Sitagliptin phosphate^[11].

Fig. 3 Structure of Sitagliptin phosphate

II. ANALYTICAL METHOD OF SURVEY OF EMPAGLIFLOZIN AND SITAGLIPTIN PHOSPHATE

Survey for the analytical method of Empagliflozin:

As per the literature survey, Table I illustrates the different analytical methods of validation of Empagliflozin, which include UV-Spectroscopy, RP-HPLC, and HPTLC.

Table I. Methods for Empagliflozin

Sr. No.	Title	Description	Ref. No.
UV-Spectrophotometric method			
1.	Development and validation of simple UV-Spectrophotometric method for the determination of Empagliflozin	Solvent: Water: Methanol (9.0:1.0% v/v) Wavelength: 224 nm Linearity: 1.0–3.0 µg/mL	12
2.	Method development and validation of Empagliflozin in bulk and pharmaceutical dosage forms using UV spectroscopy	Solvent: Ethanol and Water Wavelength: 223 nm Linearity: 1-30µg/mL	13
Reverse “Phase High Performance Liquid Chromatography(RP-HPLC)			
3.	RP-HPLC method for quantification of Empagliflozin in pharmaceutical formulation	Mobile Phase: Methanol:Water (70:30% v/v) Stationary phase: C18G column (250x4.6mm, 5µm) Linearity: 10–90µg/mL Flowrate: 1mL per min	14
4.	Development and validation of Stability Indicating RP-HPLC method for Empagliflozin	Mobile Phase: Methanol:Water (70:30% v/v) Stationary phase: Phenomenex C18 column (250x4.6mm, 5µm) Linearity: 2–14µg/mL Flowrate: 1.0mL/min	15
5.	Empagliflozin: HPLC-based analytical method development and application to pharmaceutical raw” material and dosage form	Mobile Phase: Water: Acetonitrile (70:30 % v/v):0.1% Trifluoroacetic acid solution (pH 4.8) Stationary phase: C18 column (250x4.6mm, 5µm) Linearity: 0.025-30µg mL Flow rate: 1.0mL/min	16
6.	A new simple method of development, validation, and forced degradation studies of Empagliflozin by using RP-HPLC	Mobile Phase: Water: Acetonitrile (45:55% v/v) Phosphate Buffer (pH:2.8) Stationary phase: Develosil ODS HG-5 RP C18 column (150x4.6mm,5µm) Flow rate: 1.0mL/min Linearity: 0–50µg/mL	17
High-Performance Thin Layer Chromatography (HPTLC)			
7.	A novel validated stability indicating method for quantification of Empagliflozin in bulk and marketed formulation by HPTLC applying experimental design approach.	Mobile Phase: Ammonium acetate (2%):Triethylamine:Isopropyl alcohol (4:1:5% v/v/v) Stationary phase: Aluminum plate which was formerly been coated with the silica gel Detection: 237nm	18

Survey for an analytical method of Empagliflozin with various API

As per the literature survey, Table II illustrates the different analytical procedure for validation of Empagliflozin with Metformin hydrochloride as well as Linagliptin. The reported methods are RP-HPLC, RP-LC, HPLC, UV-Spectroscopy and HPTLC.

Table II. Methods for Empagliflozin in combination

Sr. No.	Title	Description	Ref. No.
Empagliflozin with Linagliptin and Metformin Hydrochloride			
1.	Development “and Validation of the RP-HPLC Method for the Simultaneous Estimation of Linagliptin, Empagliflozin, and Metformin in Solid Dosage Forms	Stationary Phase: Kromosil (250mmX4.6mm;5µm) column Mobile Phase: Buffer:Acetonitrile (45:55% v/v) Wavelength: 233nm Retention time: 2.787min EMPA; 3.419 min MET; 2.370 min LIN	19
2	Simultaneous quantification of empagliflozin, linagliptin, and metformin hydrochloride in bulk and synthetic mixture by RP-LC method	Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile:Methanol:Water (27:20:53% v/v/v) Stationary Phase: Phenomenex C18 column (250mmx4.6mm; 5µm) Wavelength: 223nm Flow rate: 1ml/min Retention time: 14.5min EMPA; 3.4min LIN; 2.01min MET	20
3.	New Validated Stability-Indicating RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous determination” of Metformin hydrochloride, Linagliptin, and Empagliflozin in bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage form	Stationary Phase: Agilent Eclipse XDB-C18 (250mm x4.6mm, 5µm) Mobile Phase: 0.1%riethylamine (pH=3) buffer and acetonitrile in the ratio 40:60 (v/v) Wavelength: 240nm Flow rate: 1ml/min Retention time: 5.412min EMPA; 3.586min LIN; 2.660 min MET	21
Empagliflozin with Linagliptin			
4.	Development and Validation of a Stability-Indicating HPLC Method for Empagliflozin and Linagliptin in Tablet Dosage Form	Stationary Phase: C ₁₈ column (BDS 250 mm X4.6 mm;5µm) Mobile Phase: 0.1% orthophosphoric acid: Acetonitrile (60:40) Wavelength: 230nm Flow rate: 1ml/min Retention time: 2.05 min EMPA; 4.10 min LIN	22
5.	Analytical Method Development and Validation for Simultaneous Estimation of Empagliflozin and Linagliptin in Bulk Drug and in Pharmaceutical Dosage Formulation by HPLC	Stationary Phase: waters acquity C18 (100x2.1mm id) Mobile Phase: methanol & water in 60:40 ratio Wavelength: 270nm Flow rate: 0.5ml/min Retention time: 1.320 min EMPA; 2.343min LIN;	23
6.	Stability Indicating Assay of Empagliflozin and Linagliptin	Mobile Phase: phosphate buffer (pH-5) & methanol (20:80) Stationary Phase: Sunniest ECO C18 (250mmx4.6mm, 5µm) Wavelength: 275nm Flow rate: 1.5ml/min	24

Empagliflozin with Metformin			
7.	A New Validated Stability Indicating RP-HPLC Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Metformin Hydrochloride and Empagliflozin in Tablet Dosage Forms	Stationary Phase: Kromosil C18 column (50mm X4.6mm; 5 μ m) Mobile Phase: Acetonitrile: 0.1% Ortho phosphoric acid (50:50% v/v) Wavelength: 260nm Flow rate: 1ml/min Run time: 6min Retention time: 3.20min EMPA; 2.19min MET	25
8.	Development and Validation of UV spectrophotometric method for Simultaneous estimation of Empagliflozin and Metformin hydrochloride in bulk drugs	Wavelength: 224nm EMPA; 230nm MET Solvent: Methanol Linearity range: 1-3 μ g/ml EMPA; 10-50 μ g/ml MET	26
9.	A Novel Validated Stability Indicating Analytical Method for Simultaneous Quantification of Metformin Hydrochloride and Empagliflozin in Bulk and Marketed Formulation by HPTLC using Box-Wilson Experimental Design Approach	Stationary Phase: Silica gel precoated plates Mobile Phase: 2% Ammonium acetate: Isopropyl alcohol:Triethyl-amine (4:6:0.1% v/v/v) Wavelength: 242nm Linearity range: 125-750ng/band EMPA; 5000 – 30000 ng/band MET	27

Survey for the analytical method of Sitagliptin phosphate

As per the literature survey, Table III illustrates the different analytical methods of validation of Sitagliptin phosphate, which include UV-Spectroscopy, and RP-HPLC.

Table III. Methods for Sitagliptin phosphate

Sr. No.	Title	Description	Ref. No.
1.	Development and Validation of RP-HPLC Method for the Estimation of Sitagliptin Phosphate in Tablet Dosage Form	Stationary Phase: Thermo scientific C18 (250x4.6mm, 5 μ m) Mobile Phase: Methanol Wavelength: 248 nm Flow rate: 1ml/min	28
2.	Development and Validation of RP-HPLC Method for Estimating Sitagliptin Phosphate in Tablet Dosage Form	Stationary Phase: Phenomenex C18 (150x4.6mm, 5 μ m) Mobile Phase: Mixture of thophosphate buffer or 0.01M Potassium dihydrogen:Methanol(50:50% v/v) pH: 2.5 Wavelength: 267nm Flow rate: 0.7ml/min	29
3.	Development and Validation of the RP-HPLC method for the estimation of Sitagliptin Phosphate in Bulk and its Tablet Dosage Form	Mobile Phase: Mixture of Potassium dihydrogen phosphate buffer:Acetonitrile (35:65% v/v) pH:3 Stationary Phase: Zorbax Eclipse XDB C18 (250x4.6mm, 5 μ m) Wavelength: 210nm Flow rate: 1ml/min	30

4.	Analytical method development and validation for some oral hypoglycemic” drugs	Mobile Phase: Mixture of Acetonitrile:Water(60:40% v/v) Stationary Phase: C18 (250x4.6mm, 5µm) Wavelength: 272nm Flow rate: 1ml per min	31
5.	Analytical “Method Development and Validation of Sitagliptin Phosphate Monohydrate in Pure and Tablet Dosage Form by UV”-Vis Spectroscopy	Wavelength: 267nm Solvent: Methanol Linearity: 20-60µg/ml	32
6.	Analytical “method development and validation of Sitagliptin phosphate monohydrate in pure and tablet dosage form by derivative spectroscopy	Wavelength: Zero order derivative λ max: 267nm in Methanol First order derivative” λ max: 213nm in Methanol Second order derivative λ max: 276nm in Methanol Linearity: 20-60µg/ml	33

Survey for the analytical method of Sitagliptin phosphate with various API

As per the literature survey, Table IV illustrates the different analytical methods of validation of Sitagliptin phosphate with Metformin, Gliclazide and Simvastatin. The methods discussed include UV spectroscopy, HPLC, along RP-HPLC.

Table IV. Methods for Sitagliptin phosphate in combination

Sr. No.	Title	Description	Ref. No.
Sitagliptin with Gliclazide			
1.	Development and Validation of Spectrophotometric method for simultaneous estimation “of Gliclazide and Sitagliptin Phosphate Monohydrate in Bulk and Pharmaceutical dosage form	Wavelength: 226 nm GLZ; 267 nm Solvent: Methanol Linearity range: 7 to 27µg/ml GLZ; 20-100µg per ml SPM	34
Sitagliptin with Metformin			
2.	Validated RP HPLC Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Metformin Hydrochloride and Sitagliptin Phosphate in Bulk Drug and Pharmaceutical Formulation	Mobile Phase: Mixture of Methanol:Acetonitrile:Phosphate buffer(20:35:45%, v/v/v) pH:8 Stationary Phase: Xterra Symmetry C18 (100x4.6mm, 5µm) Wavelength: 254nm Flow rate: 1ml per min	35
3.	Stability-Indicating RP-HPLC Method and its Validation for Analysis of Sitagliptin &Metformin in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Form	Mobile Phase: Mixture of OPA buffer:Acetonitrile (80:20%,v/v) Stationary Phase: AGILENT CN (250x4.6mm, 5µm) Flow rate: 1ml/min Wavelength: 205nm	36

4	Development and Validation of RP-HPLC Method for Determination of Metformin and Sitagliptin in Bulk and Pharmaceutical Dosage Form.	Stationary Phase: Intersil-BDS C18 (250x4.6mm, 5 μ m) Mobile Phase: Mixture of Water ⁺ :Methanol (60:40%v/v) Wavelength: 258nm Flow rate: 1ml/min	37
5.	Development and Validation of RP-HPLC Method for Simultaneous Estimation of Metformin Hydrochloride and Sitagliptin "Phosphate from Bulk and Combined Dosage Form	Mobile Phase: Mixture of Phosphate buffer: Methanol: Acetonitrile (50:30:20%, v/v/v) pH:4 Stationary Phase: BDS HYPERSILC18 (250x4.6mm, 5 μ m) Wavelength: 253nm Flow rate: 0.8ml/min	38
6.	Method development and validation of sitagliptin and metformin using reverse phase HPLC method in bulk and tablet dosage form	Stationary Phase: Hypersil BDS C18 (100x4.6mm, 5 μ m) Mobile Phase: Mixture of Potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate buffer:Methanol (50:50% v/v) pH:8.5 Wavelength: 215nm Flow rate: 1ml/min	39
Sitagliptin with Simvastatin			
7.	Stability- indicating RP- HPLC Method for the Simultaneous Determination of Sitagliptin and Simvastatin in Tablets	Stationary Phase: Qualisil BDS C8 (250x4.6mm, 5 μ m) Mobile Phase: Mixture of Methanol:Water(70:30% v/v) pH:3 Wavelength: 253nm Flow rate: 1ml/min	40
8.	Development and Validation of RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of Sitagliptin phosphate and Simvastatin in bulk and tablet dosage form	Stationary Phase: aHi-Q Si C18(250x4.6mm, 5 μ m) Mobile Phase: Mixture of Acetonitrile:Methanol:10mM Phosphate buffer (65:25:10%, v/v/v) pH:4 Wavelength: 250nm Flow rate: 1.2ml/min	41
9.	Novel RP-HPLC Method for Simultaneous Determination of Sitagliptin and Simvastatin in Bulk and Tablet" Dosage Form	Mobile Phase: Mixture of 10mM Phosphate buffer:Acetonitrile:Methanol(45:35:20% v/v) pH: 6.3 Stationary Phase: Welchrom C18 (250x4.6mm, 5 μ m) Wavelength: 255nm Flow rate: 1ml/min	42

Survey for the analytical method of Empagliflozin with Sitagliptin phosphate

As per the literature survey, Table V illustrates the different analytical methods of validation of empagliflozin with Sitagliptin phosphate. The reported methods are RP-HPLC and UV-Spectroscopy.

Table V. Methods for Empagliflozin and Sitagliptin phosphate

Sr. No.	Title	Description	Ref. No.
1.	Development and Validation of Simultaneous Equation Method for Estimation of Sitagliptin Phosphate and Empagliflozin in bulk form by UV Spectroscopy	Solvent: Methanol: Water (5:5) Wavelength: 267nm SITA and 276.2nm EMPA Linearity: 50-250µg/ml	43
Sitagliptin and Empagliflozin with Metformin			
2.	Reverse “Phase Chromatographic Method of Analysis for Assay and Content Uniformity Estimation of Drug Substance Sitagliptin, Metformin, and Empagliflozin from Available” Marketed Formulation	Stationary Phase: X-Bridge C18 (250mm*4.6mm*5µm) Mobile Phase: 0.1% Trifluoroacetic acid Buffer 40%: Methanol 40%:Acetonitrile 20% Wavelength: 224nm Flow rate: 1.0mL/min	44

III. DISCUSSION

The literature discloses that several analytical techniques were developed created for measuring empagliflozin and sitagliptin phosphate, whether they are used alone or alongside other medications. However, very few techniques exist to estimate Empagliflozin and Sitagliptin phosphate simultaneously As a result, we set out to develop and validate an easy-to-use method that is accurate, precise, and specific for measuring both sitagliptin phosphate and empagliflozin using spectrophotometry and chromatography. The method was successfully developed and validated following ICH standards, ensuring its reliability and effectiveness.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study focuses on creating and validating different spectrophotometric and chromatographic techniques to measure empagliflozin and sitagliptin. The methods discussed include RP-HPLC, HPTLC, TLC, and UV spectrophotometry. These techniques have been demonstrated to effectively provide accurate, precise, and reproducible ways. The findings suggest that a comprehensive understanding of these methods can enhance future research and development efforts in the pharmaceutical field, particularly for the selected drugs.

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